

The Best Practices in the Knowledge Management of Academic Libraries: The Realization of Equality According To the Laws

Pr. Nadjiba Badi Boukemidja
Professor at University of Algiers
Benyoucef Benkhedda
Faculty of law, Algiers, Algeria
Email : n.boukemidja@univ-alger.dz

Abstract: The two main conceptions of "public services" or "services of general interest" are subject, on the one hand, to the functional conception, which emphasizes the objectives, purposes, missions or, obligations of public service; on the other hand, the organic conception, which assimilates the public service to the public entity . Thus, librarians only contribute to providing material, in the form of collections and online resources but also conferences, debates, exhibitions. For this, a climate of competition is necessary, and the libraries as an economic actors must respect the rules of the law of competition.

Keywords: Libraries, public service, competition law, intellectual property, management.

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1. Introduction

Knowledge management is more than ever a strategic priority for libraries. With rapid digitization and the growing complexity of information, it is essential to know how to manage and make the most of internal knowledge to remain competitive. Knowledge management is not just about collecting information: it's also about organizing it, sharing it and applying it in the best possible way.

Libraries are at a critical juncture. We heard much hand wringing about whether public libraries would become obsolete and we faced constant questions about how libraries can remain relevant in the age of online information. Nearly 20 years later, libraries have successfully transformed themselves from being chiefly about materials to being community anchors for formal and informal learning, technology access, workforce development, and community engagement. (Mark SMITH, 2019).

Thus, libraries can practice their functions under competition law. Except that, Competition law and policy are not always high up the agenda for libraries. As public services, we are interested in overall approaches to the public sector. As part of the research and education infrastructure, we care about policies in these areas.

However, competition law and policy do have a major effect on libraries and the world in which they operate. It is therefore an interesting angle for advocacy and lobbying work. It is also a contested area, with ongoing discussions about how to understand and promote competition. (Competition and libraries, 2020).

To do this, we pose the following problem: What is the best management of libraries, in a competitive environment, and to ensure the public interest?

In order to answer this question, we must follow the following plan:

- 1- Economic activity of libraries.
- 2 - The personal delimitation of the application of competition law on libraries.
- 3- The intervention of libraries in relation to the public service.
- 4-Knowledge management and libraries.
- 5-Intellectual property rights within libraries.
- 6-The fairness of the competition undertaken by libraries.

Depending on the nature of the subject, which represents the intersection between the public service of libraries and competition law, we will use the descriptive method linked to some notions of competition law, as well as the analytical method in order to reach certain conclusions.

2. Economic activity of libraries

As some authors remind us, "the relationship between competition and equality is particularly ambiguous".(Claude Lucas DE LEYSSAAC 2002).

In essence, when libraries engage in economic competition, they set themselves the goal of securing the best market share for their business, while respecting the limits to the preservation of a sufficient degree of competition.

The horizon of the libraries is therefore to do better than their competitor. The ambition is therefore not to remain equal but to always do better.

Equal application of competition law

Following on from what has been demonstrated above, we will note that the principle of equality extends from the sphere of general private law to public persons, such as public libraries. The private sphere comes, therefore, to encroach on the public library, in the limit where this one does not exercise prerogatives of public powers.

Public libraries act with other economic operators on an equal scale. Thus, in the case of public service missions, they will use their prerogatives of public powers. The principle of equality between the public library and the private actor is thus broken.

The rupture of equality

As soon as the public library intervenes on the market for the accomplishment of a mission of public service, by exercising these prerogatives of public powers, appears then a rupture of equality with the other economic actors.

We can consider that this theory is applicable in the case of Google on the digital library market. This is because of the protection that property law provides to the Google Books database. Let us recall that intellectual property law protects the database created by the creator of the digital library. This protection aims to prevent any individual from using digitized data without the consent of the database creator. From a competition point of view, this protection creates a monopoly, as the position of Google Books today attests.

Indeed, all protected digitized works can no longer be exploited by a competitor in order to build up its own database. The normal play of competition is therefore distorted by the application of the law. One speaks then of "de jure monopoly as opposed to de facto monopoly". (Marie-Charlotte LANDA, 2021)

3. The intervention of libraries in relation to public service

The main principle governing the concept of public service is the need to meet the needs of the general interest without interruption in the hours determined by the institution. The organization of work in each public service must therefore allow for this continuity. It is, therefore, necessary to ensure that schedules are set up in such a way as to guarantee continuity of service whenever it is defined by the establishment as being necessary for the public service. (University of Angers, 2020).

Public library intervention limited to public service

The notion of public service is in crisis .(Jean Ludovic SILICANI, 2008). From the moment that the intervention of the library on the economic market is accepted, with the only limit that the latter intervenes for missions of public service. By analogy, it is therefore forbidden for the public person to distort competition. The public service is an extended notion in law, it is defined as any activity aiming to satisfy a need of general interest. (Pierre ESPUGLAS, 2002).

Intervention of libraries outside of these public service activities

In this section, we will deal with the case where the library intervenes outside its field of action, outside its public service activities.(Sebastien FERRARI, 2008).

The legality of public initiative in economic matters remains subject to the respect of the freedom of trade and industry (CE Ass, requête n° 247298), which is a general principle of law(CE Sect, request n° 92099) .

These general principles are now directly derived from competition law. The library can only intervene in the market on the condition that it respects certain equality of arms with private operators. Thus, when it acts as an economic operator, the library must not take advantage of the prices it charges of its status, its particular situation, its resources, or the means allocated to it under its other public service missions. The price proposed must therefore reflect the full cost of the service. This control of the library's behavior on the market is reminiscent of the principle of fair competition, of which there are a few reminders in jurisprudence. (CE, 1965).

4. Knowledge management and libraries

How to manage knowledge will become an important subject facing libraries in the near future. Knowledge management in libraries should be focused on effective research and development of knowledge, creation of knowledge bases, exchange and sharing of knowledge between library staffs, training of library staff, speeding up explicit processing of the implicit knowledge and realizing of its sharing. (Senthur VELMURUGAN,2012).

The context of knowledge management

The key idea driving knowledge management (KM) is that knowledge is a strategic asset that must be managed. It should be managed as an asset or resource just like land, capital and labour. In the present information and knowledge era, knowledge as an intangible asset has taken precedence over traditional organizational resources such as capital and labour. KM has attracted a series of definitions, explanations and conceptualizations due to its interdisciplinary nature.

However, it can be inferred that any attempt to define and conceptualize KM must take into account the two major types of knowledge (explicit and tacit) and the circumstances that led to the development of KM. Knowledge management involves the organization and harnessing of the knowledge assets in order to achieve individual and corporate goals.

In the current knowledge environment, it has become essential for individuals to maintain, develop and market their skills to gain a competitive advantage in the job market in both the short and long term. Jain (2011) viewed personal knowledge management (PKM) as managing and maintaining personal knowledge which a person already has to enrich an individual knowledge database.

It will enable the individual to retrieve knowledge time effectively so as to use, re-use and mobilize it for personal benefit or benefit of the organization or the community. PKM is a tool which can equip knowledge workers with the necessary skills to manage their knowledge. (Anike ANGELA, Festus AGHAGBO, Nnamdi AZIKIWE, 2020).

Subsequently, knowledge is difficult to grasp and define, but it is undoubtedly the most important asset in the knowledge economy. As information is becoming more and more available, translating it into knowledge is both more demanding and important. As information and knowledge workers, librarians must be aware of this. It can be said that while data is essentially numbers and letters without meaning, data presented in a context that makes sense is information. Knowledge is further developed when information is combined with experience, context, interpretation and reflection. (Hilde DALAND, 2016)

Knowledge management used in university libraries

The importance of innovation within the field of library and information studies cannot be overstated; libraries are no longer expected to simply exist as a welcoming repository for physical books. With decreased budgets and an exponential increase in digital literacy needs, libraries are forced to continually adapt to these changes or risk becoming obsolete to the community they are trying to serve.

These ongoing adaptations often lead to innovative new ideas that positively impact the services that are provided by libraries for their patrons, particularly in academic libraries where the library users are at the leading edge of research and development. (McKayla GODDARD, 2020).

KM can be used in academic libraries to improve the situations in which they find themselves. Articulating the principles underlying this management theory provides a useful framework for managers' use in improving their organization's performance. These principles, (a) organizational improvement, (b) alignment with institutional mission, (c) recorded and shared knowledge, (d) communication reflecting multi-level dialogue, and (e) continual planning and assessment, should guide the work of managers. (Sandra SHOROPSHIRE, Jenny Lynne SEMENZA, Regina KOURY, 2020).

In the library environment, it is widely acknowledged that the application of KM improves library operational effectiveness, such as improved access to information resources, and facilitates services innovation through the enhancement of internal and external knowledge sharing and the creation of new knowledge.

Although "knowledge management has much to offer to the management of libraries and advancement of the LIS professions", the adoption of KM by library and information science (LIS) professionals is very slow. The ambiguity of the terminology, on the one hand, and the disagreement among LIS professionals regarding its relation to information management (IM), on the other, constitute significant barriers for their involvement in KM. (Maria KOLONIARI, Kostas FASSOULIS, 2016).

The research findings indicate that the creation of new knowledge in academic libraries is enhanced not only by the implementation of a clear and well-planned knowledge strategy, but first and foremost by the establishment of a knowledge-conducive culture and practices built on open communications, a team-based structure and supported by the use of technology tools. (Maria KOLONIARI, Eftichia VRAIMAKI, Kostas FASSOULIS, 2019).

In a knowledge society, universities play a decisive role as 'knowledge-intensive organisations', specialising in its creation, organisation and dissemination. Building on their mission, universities can help establish such a society by managing knowledge geared to strengthening interaction with their surrounding community. In a scenario characterised by the ongoing evolution of ICTs, libraries are in a position to effectively manage all the knowledge produced in a university as a key to innovation. (Ana PACIOS, 2019).

As for further research, possible perception disparities between employees and management regarding organizational culture and KM practices should be examined. As recent research reveals a huge gap between what employees and their leaders believe about organizational culture, such a comparative examination would shed some light on what library leadership should do to improve culture and enhance knowledge creation and innovation.

Furthermore, the influence of specific leadership styles and types of incentives should be studied, as they could reveal important aspects of knowledge creation and innovation mechanisms in libraries. Finally, the strong interaction between service

innovation and process innovation that emerged from this study's findings suggests the need for more in-depth examination of this relation. (Maria KOLONIARI, Eftichia VRAIMAKI, Kostas FASSOULIS, 2018)

5. Intellectual property rights within libraries

Transforming from building boundaries to internet protocols, the library also face some copyright issues. The transformation is begun to first stage that the automation of cataloguing through computer. The second stage is when library collections are digitalized, and the third stage when these digitized documents uploaded on internet to access from globalized world. The conflict of copyright act is take places in second and third stage. Copyright is bunch of rights it includes the right of replica, issue of copies, communication to the public, alteration, and translation. These are transferable rights. All these effected while a work processed through digitization. (Tara CHAND, 2018).

The classic form of intellectual rights linked to libraries

As a result of recent developments in information formats and the open access movement, everyday copyright law affects the way libraries provide information to their users and every outcome can directly affect the future of libraries (American Library Association and libraries face more and more complicated intellectual property and copyright issues than in the past.

Traditionally, libraries are leaders in trying to maintain a balance of power between copyright holders and users or at the very least advocate for intellectual freedom and promote access to information (Nilsson, 2015) in keeping with the fundamental principles outlined in local and international constitutions. (Zakir HOSSAIN, 2020).

In any educational institute librarian plays a key role in many spheres, including copyright. The main role of librarian is to make available of library collections to students and faculty in support of teaching, learning, research and scholarship. Libraries are creatures of the historical and statutory balance in copyright law. Libraries lend materials based on the First Sale doctrine. Libraries share materials and preserve works under specific provisions for libraries in the Act. Libraries are often the only entities that provide access to the vast majority of copyrighted works that lose market vitality long before the expiration of the copyrights, and are often the only entities that preserve public domain materials. (Firdous MAQBOOL MIR, 2016).

Furthermore, libraries especially academic libraries in the developing world are on cross roads. They are confused on whether to support the IP protection so as to generate the income of the authors or support the open access drive where the knowledge is made available to everyone without any commercial implications. There is an immediate requirement for universities to take any one route so as to protect the interest of knowledge custodians. If they take first approach though the receiver has to pay for the usage, the contributor also will get benefit out of it. If they take second route both receiver and contributor need not have any commercials in their transactions. (Mahesh YARANAL, 2012).

Likewise, the intellectual property issues are mainly issues of copyright and fair use, and as a result copyright and fair use despite Schlipp's inclusion on other types of intellectual property. Nevertheless, throughout the book Schlipp demonstrates that all types of libraries—academic, school, public, and special—encounter a range of intellectual property and information rights issues on a regular basis. *Intellectual Property and Information Rights for Librarians* contains both conceptual and practical knowledge of those issues and provides librarians with a good foundation for daily library practice. (Kathy WATTS, 2020).

Thus, exclusive rights are an intended feature of intellectual property law, which gives copyright holders (here, the publishers) the right to control distribution of the copyright work as a way to encourage creativity. However, those licensing terms may also cause difficulties for libraries. Because licenses to libraries include a limited distribution right, they are nearly always more expensive than licenses to individuals—often several times more expensive. As an example, for one publisher, an individual e-book copy costs \$14.99; a library copy costs \$84. Macmillan eventually ended this policy in March 2020. (Congressional Research Service, 2020).

The digitalization of libraries

The Digital Library “DL” of the 21st century is a hybrid form of a library that deviates from the traditional book-keeping library of the past. The term “Digital Library” was coined because of the Internet and refers to an evolved new form of a library that could cover a wide range of information services.¹⁸ The DL of the 21st century is not merely a host of digitized books and collections, but rather it's an integrator of information management systems, that consists of important elements such as data and metadata, human contribution (creators, users, managers), IT infrastructures (computers, networks, software) which are all orchestrated with the aim to organize, manage, and make available to, i.e. open access to, knowledge and information to library-users. (Dionysia KALLINIKOU, 2009).

The digitization of the collection by the library covers under the right of reproduction and adaptation. Reproduction includes the storing of a work in any medium by electronic means and adaptation includes rearrangement or alteration in work. During the digitization all these process occurs which come under the right of adaptation and alteration (Tara CHAND, 2018).

Online contents are more vulnerable when compared with printed and digital resources. Copyright protection of these resources is really herculean task for the librarians. The issues involved in the protection are dynamic and cannot fit in one thumb rule. Managing online content is multidisciplinary in nature and require thorough technical knowledge.

In case of commercial online database, the publishers do not take appropriate security measures to safe guard their contents and always insist librarians to take action to protect the copyright. Since librarians are directly involved in negotiating the price and license mode, the management also expect the librarians to handle the crisis. Lack of technical knowledge and non-cooperation of management put the librarians in to trouble. (Mahesh YARANAL, 2012).

Comparison between traditional and digital libraries, it is no doubt that digital libraries are distinguished from the other ones in many aspects as follows:

- Saving the researchers' time and overcoming spatial and temporal barriers between the countries, the researcher does not need to get into what information to travel or like that. This is an application of the principle that information reaches the beneficiaries.
- Ability to control the content and electronic sources of information, where information and data can be organized, stored and saved in ways that are accurate as effective as they can be easily updated.
- Utilization of great potential for digital libraries and technologies in terms of the correlation information and the use of Multimedia and Hypertext which enable the researcher an access to information as much as he needs about his research subject.
- Possibility of participating in electronic sources in sharing digital and resources between libraries. This document can read or use the information from source of more than a researcher at the same time, which increases effectiveness of information source and increasing the benefit from it.
- Facilitating borrowing operations between libraries and various information institutions, in addition to increasing cooperation between the libraries in various fields for achieving a better level of services provision to beneficiaries, besides enhancing communication with various information facilities in quick and guaranteed means. (Mohammad NIQRESH, 2019) .

Licenses to libraries often expire after a certain amount of time (for example, two years), after the e-book has been checked out a certain number of times (for example, twenty-six), or both. Most e-book licenses to libraries will also provide that each e-book may only be checked out by a single user at once, just as a physical copy may only be checked out by a single user at any given time. Certain publishers have experimented with more restrictive policies.

For example, in November 2019 Macmillan implemented a policy where it would not license e-books to libraries during the first eight weeks after a title's release. Macmillan explained that those early weeks were key for profits and that libraries were "cannibalizing sales." This led to many libraries boycotting Macmillan purchases entirely. Macmillan eventually ended this policy in March 2020. (Congressional Research Service, 2020).

In the same context, and with regard to the application of artificial intelligence on library practices, the University of Rhode Island opened its Artificial Intelligence Lab in September 2018, the first AI facility housed in a library. The cross-disciplinary lab is open to all students, faculty, and staff for research into robotics, wearable technology, smart cities, and technological ethics. The Cambridge (Mass.) Public Library partnered with Massachusetts Institute of Technology Libraries and Harvard's metaLAB to host the installation of a "Laughing Room," in which participants enter an artificially intelligent room that plays a laugh track whenever something is said that the room's algorithm deems funny. (Steve ZALUSKY, 2020).

6. The fairness of the competition undertaken by libraries

Constructive participation and the development of democracy depend on satisfactory education as well as on free and unlimited access to knowledge, thought, culture and information. We now live in an information society and in a knowledge economy where knowledge management is essential. "Knowledge-based economy is not an ordinary branch of the economy. It is a compatible system of legal and economical preconditions, as well as managerial and economic mechanisms together with modern technologies and human recourses. (Ziaur RAHMAN, 2013).

For books and eBooks, three alternative price models exist. Firstly, in the wholesale model, publishers set the price of books and sell them to retailers at a substantial discount. Retailers sell the books to consumers at prices they decide. They pay the other participants of the supply chain (especially the authors), and keep the profit— or swallow the loss. They can sell popular books at a significant discount, in order to widen their market share. Secondly, in the agency model, retailers become “agents” through which publishers sell books directly to consumers. The agency model does not allow for discounting; contracts provide publishers with some control over retail prices. Thirdly, in the Resale Price Maintenance or RPM model (fixed book prices), the publisher determines the price at which booksellers sell a book title to consumers. (Francoise BENHAMOU, 2015).

For international texts, it is important to underline the position of the World Intellectual Property Organization (W.I.P.O.) which administers the Paris Convention for the Protection of Industrial Property, of March 20, 1883.

Article 10 bis of the convention lists the cases of unfair competition that should be avoided in order not to harm the competitor, and also in order not to disrupt the competitive environment.

Moreover, the cases are the following:

(1) The countries of the Union are bound to assure to nationals of such countries effective protection against unfair competition.

(2) Any act of competition contrary to honest practices in industrial or commercial matters constitutes an act of unfair competition.

(3) The following, in particular, shall be prohibited:

(i) all acts of such a nature as to create confusion by any means whatever with the establishment, the goods, or the industrial or commercial activities, of a competitor;

(ii) false allegations in the course of trade of such a nature as to discredit the establishment, the goods, or the industrial or commercial activities, of a competitor;

(iii) indications or allegations the use of which in the course of trade is liable to mislead the public as to the nature, the manufacturing process, the characteristics, the suitability for their purpose, or the quantity, of the goods.

eLending and eBook platforms, are examples of the two-sided platforms mentioned earlier. In the library lending field, OverDrive has become a major player, building up a strong enough position to be able to negotiate with publishers.

Clearly, libraries themselves can benefit – at least in the short term – from a single platform that can negotiate good prices from publishers. Publishers who are keen to access library readers may of course be less happy to have to receive less than they would like.

However, more questions emerge around whether a company like OverDrive really allows libraries to provide the reader advisory support that they would like, and the degree to which it provides the data that libraries traditionally rely on for decision-making. The company's recent buy-out indicates that it also making a strong level of profit. This is why library-led platforms such as SimplyE are interesting, as they provide competition for commercial operations such as OverDrive – in other words, libraries can always go somewhere else. (Competition and libraries, 2020).

At the same time, during the process of digitization of works, in the United States, Google came up against the protection of copyright. Sued by the Association of American Publishers (A.A.P) and the Authors Guild, the search engine reached a settlement in 2009. In addition to paying 125 million dollars to these two associations, Google undertakes to ask for the authorization of the rights holders before putting online books still protected by copyright and still available in bookstores.

On the other hand, for works still protected but whose restocking is impossible for bookstores, it will be up to the rights holders to indicate their opposition to the exploitation of their works. "France: the trial of Google against La Martinière begins," ActuaLitté, available on ActuaLitté, (accessed December 4, 2012).

7. Conclusion

To conclude it is important to emphasize the necessity of knowledge, which is provided by libraries as part of the public service. The latter is also imposed by the rules of competition, which impose limits not to be crossed, and also customs and habits to be respected.

Within the framework of the transparency of the competitive environment, we make the following recommendations:

- The public interest of libraries should not prevent them from having economic activities. In order to strengthen the service provided by the libraries, and also to assume the role of the economic actor in the competitive market.

- University libraries are required to change at an ever-increasing rate to support their alma mater. And the concept of knowledge Management and its positive impact on innovation within the organization is not new. The operation of KMS and ICT in university libraries is still incomplete. Area Future research may include incorporating customer knowledge into institutions KMS, and the increasing influence of different organizational cultures use technology in the workplace.

- If the university library wants to the current challenging environment is better for the needs of readers, library directors should be cautious design and implement a knowledge-centric strategy create new knowledge to be realized. Factor Promote knowledge-related

behavior think seriously. Since the organization culture becomes the most critical knowledge creation facilitators, library leaders must focus on shaping a culture promote an environment for knowledge sharing through appropriate incentives.

-The open access movement brought new hope and reduce the burden of librarians returning to the service motto, not the middleman business knowledge broker. At these critical moments, librarians must handle the situation by educating and equipping yourself to control the situation Intellectual property and technology crisis.

-Copyright law must be revised to accommodate digitization environment and safety precautions in the current development of information technology Intellectual property at the national and international level. Librarians and information scientists should understand the intellectual property regulations in the existing laws of your country.

-The distinction between prohibited competition and unfair competition is necessary. Thus, the practices of libraries when they are contrary to the texts, it implies that we are facing a forbidden competition. However, when the practices of libraries are contrary to custom and usage, they qualify as unfair competition. In both cases, it is a violation of the competitive environment of libraries.

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